

Figures for the ELAIS-S1 Field

Figure 1. Corresponding to Fig. 5 in the main paper. The black line is the color-color cut, $Z - K_s = 0.4(B - Z) - 0.65$, used to trim SED-selected stars; see Appendix D of the main paper for more information.

Figure 2. Corresponding to Fig. 6 in the main paper.

Figure 3. Corresponding to Fig. 7 in the main paper.

Figure 4. Corresponding to Fig. 8 in the main paper.

Figure 5. Corresponding to Fig. 10 in the main paper.

Figure 6. Corresponding to Fig. 11 in the main paper.

Figure 9. Corresponding to Fig. 17 in the main paper.

Figure 7. Corresponding to Fig. 15 in the main paper.

Figure 8. Corresponding to Fig. 16 in the main paper.

Figure 10. Corresponding to Fig. 18 in the main paper.

Figure 11. Corresponding to Fig. 19 in the main paper.

Figure 12. Corresponding to Fig. 20 in the main paper.

Figure 13. Corresponding to Fig. 21 in the main paper.

Figure 14. Corresponding to Fig. 22 in the main paper.

Figure 15. Corresponding to Fig. 30 in the main paper. The number of good bands drops below 10 at i -band magnitude of 23.6, which is slightly brighter than that for W-CDF-S (≈ 24). About 30% of our sources are brighter than this nominal depth.

Figure 16. Corresponding to Fig. 31 in the main paper.